

Quantum Bound State Phase $\exp(i dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle)$ and Hydrodynamics

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In a previous note (1), we argued that $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle)$ where $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln W$ mimicking the behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ for a free quantum particle. In this note, we consider that for the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, a shift from x to $x+dx$ leads to: $P(p/x+dx) = P(p/x) \exp(i dx (\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle)) = P(p/x)(1 + i dx (\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle))$. We note that in shifting from x to $x+dx$ the overall sum of probability should not change, so $P(p/x+dx) = P(p/x) + P(p/x) g(p,x)$. If one assumes that $g(p,x)$ is a function of p alone, the simplest solution is $g(p) = \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$. If one considers $\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x+dx) = \sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x) = \Delta KE$ then this should be equal to $\text{Force}(x) dx$.

We also consider classical hydrodynamical equations and compare these with modified equations applying to the bound state quantum situation. The two sets of equations are very similar with density in the classical case being replaced with $W(x)\exp(-iEt)$, the wavefunction, and E energy or $V(x)$ (potential) terms replaced with $2E$ or $2V$ (i.e. also 2Force). In a previous note, we had considered hydrodynamical equations with the restriction $2m=1$ which is too strong. Here any m (mass) may be used.

Phase with Shift in x

In (1), we argued that quantum mechanics of a free particle is based on the statistical idea of equal probability everywhere in space, but also on the idea that a particle tracks its path in a cyclical way based on px i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. We further argued that this idea may be extended to a bound particle using:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle) \text{ where } \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln W \text{ with } W(x) = \text{the wavefunction} \quad ((1))$$

Extending to $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ one has:

$$P(p/x+dx) = P(p/x) \exp[i dx (\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle)] \quad ((2))$$

This is similar to $\exp(ipx)$, but with p replaced with $[\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle]$ and has the appearance of a kind of probability wave motion relative to an average (like center-of-mass) motion $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$, although $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ is based on interference of $\exp(ipx)$'s.

It may be noted that if $P(p/x+dx) = P(p/x) + P(p/x)g(p)$ then:

$$1 = \sum_p P(p/x+dx) = \sum_p P(p/x) \text{ so } \sum_p P(p/x) g(p) = 0$$

The simplest solution for this is $g(p) = [p - \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle]$ which matches ((2)). It is interesting that the quantum mechanical result is also the simplest one.

Thus, not only $W(x)$ shifts like a “wave”, but conditional $P(p/x)$ as well, but with p replaced by $p - \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$.

This suggests that the difference in average kinetic energy between x and $x+dx$ should be:

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m P(p/x) (p - \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle) = -dV/dx \quad dx \quad ((3))$$

Equation ((3)) is nothing more than d/dx of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Hydrodynamics

The equations of hydrodynamics (2 p98) follow from classical statistical mechanical considerations and seem to be a little different from bound state quantum mechanical results. Nevertheless there seems to be a strong link between the two, we argue. One may begin with the classical continuity equation. We set $m=1$.

$$d/dt (\text{density}) + d/dx (\text{density } u) = 0 \quad ((4a)) \quad d/dt = \text{partial derivative}$$

We replace density with $W(x)\exp(-iEt)$, the wavefunction, and $u = -i d/dx \ln W$. Then ((4a)) for a free quantum particle needs to be modified to:

$$2 d/dt (W) + d/dx (W u) = 0 \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{For a free particle:}$$

$dW/dx = -iE W$ Following ideas used in generalizing the Klein-Gordon equation to add a potential, we replace E with $E-V$ if a potential is present. Thus:

$$-i 2(E-V)W + d/dx (Wu) = 0 \quad ((5)) \quad \text{even for } u = -i d/dx \ln W \text{ i.e. a bound state}$$

((4b)) is now a continuity type equation, but is also equivalent to a conservation of energy equation. The two are not independent. The issue of the extra 2 coefficient of d/dt seems to be linked to the known issue that $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ yields a phase velocity of $\frac{1}{2} v$ and not v . This seems to carry over even into a bound state.

The classical momentum conservation hydrodynamics equation is:

$$d/dt (\text{density } \langle v \rangle) + d/dx \langle \text{density } v \rangle - \text{density } F = 0 \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where } F = -dV/dx \text{ and } d/dt \text{ is a partial derivative}$$

Again we replace density with $W(x)\exp(-iEt)$ and the first term on the LHS is: $-2i(E-V) W u$ and F changes to $2F$. Then, for a bound state:

$$-i(E-V)u + dW/dx \langle vv \rangle + W d/dx \langle vv \rangle - W 2F = 0 \quad ((7))$$

$W \frac{d\langle vv \rangle}{dx} - 2WF = 0$ as it is d/dx of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

$-i2(E-V)u W + dW/dx \langle vv \rangle = 0$ using $u = -i \ln W/dx$ and $\langle vv \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W$

It seems that in this approach, d/dt is replaced with $2d/dt$ leading to E or $E-V$ becoming $2E$ or $2(E-V)$ and $-dV/dx$ becoming $-2dV/dx$. In other words, energy terms seem to scale by 2 in order to have consistency between the "classical" hydrodynamical equations with density replaced by $W(x)\exp(-iEt)$ and quantum bound states.

Consider the evaluation of : $d/dx \langle W pp \rangle$ in ((6)) using $d/dx P(p/x)$ and dW/dx from ((1)) and ((2))

$$d/dx \sum W P(p/x) pp = \sum dW/dx P(p/x) pp + \sum W pp dP(p/x)/dx$$

$$= \sum W(u) P(p/x) pp + \sum W pp P(p/x) (p-u)$$

$$= Wu \langle pp \rangle + W\{\langle ppp \rangle - u \langle pp \rangle\} = W \langle ppp \rangle \quad ((8))$$

((8)) may be combined with $-i2(E-V)u W = \langle pp \rangle (-1) W (d \ln W/dx)$ to yield $-dV/dx$.

This is again consistent with taking d/dx of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the effect of shifting $P(p/x+dx) = P(p/x)\exp(i dx (p-\langle p \rangle))$ based on $W(x+dx) = W(x)\exp(i \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle dx)$. Here $P(p/x)$ is conditional probability. Conditional probability seems to change infinitesimally as a probability wave with p taken relative to the average p i.e. $\langle p \rangle$, almost like a center-of-mass calculation. We also note that a change of the order $(p-\langle p \rangle)P(p/x)$ is the simplest p dependent form which is zero on average, thus conserving probability as one moves from one x point to another.

We also consider the relationship between classical hydrodynamical and bound state quantum equations. The two resemble each other closely, we argue, with density in the classical equations being replaced with $W(x)\exp(-iEt)$, (the wavefunction) and energy E or $V(x)$ (potential terms) replaced with $2E$ and $2V$ (also $2F$). In an early note, we considered hydrodynamical equations with $2m=1$, but such a strong restriction is not needed and any mass may be used.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco, R. Phase Shift of $\exp[i \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle dx]$ for Bound Quantum Systems (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1983)

